

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTRODUCING AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF CHEMISTRY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The problems of introducing an integrative approach in improving the quality of chemical education and the main factors and methods of solving it are described. Considerations are given on the development of the concept of valence based on an integrative approach.*

Key words: *Chemistry education, quality of education, chemistry, integrative approach, integration*

Introduction. Humanity is living on the threshold of the age of highly developed technology, information technology, demographic and environmental crises. In such conditions, only a well-rounded generation with comprehensive knowledge will achieve great success in the future.

This generation will be tasked with saving the mother planet. Also, they are entrusted with the responsibility of solving globally important problems such as rational and economical use of Earth's reserves, spiritual upliftment of man, preservation of ecological balance. World pedagogic scientists emphasize the need to bring up young people with integrative knowledge of general education subjects. For this reason, the educational system of more than 70 developed countries is based on providing integrated education to young people.

Great attention is paid to this issue in the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers and the orders of the relevant ministries related to the continuous education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The urgency of the problem. The acceleration of the development of society, the growth of science and technology, the wide spread of information technology, in order to turn the 21st century into a century of peace, is leading humanity to a new society of nations, a deeply integrated economic space, and a unified information and communication system. [1].

Therefore, it is necessary to implement a well-founded integration of education at the level of DTS requirements. This should ultimately ensure quality education and lead to the training of competitive personnel.

The main part. The continuous increase in the number of subjects taught at school has created an overload for students. The main way to solve this problem is to establish integrated education [2].

The integration of sciences that study the laws of nature and society, their convergence and convergence is an objective process. Man is a component of nature, the main object of study of sciences.

Due to the fact that man is not only a biological, but also a social being, the mechanical, physical, chemical, biological and social laws of the material world are embodied in him in a solid combination.

Explaining the interdependent development of the events and phenomena that occur in nature and society, and the relations between them, based on the integration of natural sciences,

forms a comprehensive system of knowledge about the organic world in the student and forms a scientific worldview.

It is tried to give in-depth knowledge about things and phenomena in the structure of some academic subjects in schools separately, from the point of view of their own academic subject. As a result, the object is divided between different academic subjects, and a whole system of knowledge about it is not formed. Therefore, it is desirable to teach it in an integrated manner [3].

Therefore, integrated education envisages a new approach to the content of knowledge given in schools from the basics of science, and its main goal is to study educational materials as a complex of logically complete problems, to form a holistic scientific picture of the world and society in the minds of students, to create scientific concepts and knowledge about nature and the place of man in it. .

Solving the problem of integration is related to the effective use of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Proper organization of this process ensures the effectiveness of teaching and increases the quality of education.

The development of school education cannot be imagined without the integration of knowledge and the differentiation of education [4].

Educational material should allow students to comprehensively analyze the studied object and help to form their interest in studying the wholeness of the universe;

- the material should be specific to the subject;
- it is necessary to express the current and prospects of the development of modern science and technology.

Media education requires an interdisciplinary approach to the integration of various subject areas taught in schools. In order to effectively solve this problem, it is necessary to prepare the various social groups of the society for the future of information from a general cultural point of view.

With the help of media education, students' skills of receiving and using information, skills of designing verbal copies in visual form, opportunities of unique understanding and application of information in their practical activities will expand. Free communication with world mass media is also ensured.

Therefore, media education should be widely used in the integration of the teaching process. It is necessary to study them in such a way that at each stage of the lesson, different elements of knowledge are combined.

The use of integrated technical means in the educational process is a factor determining the direction of "educational technology" and is focused on the organization of information transmission service and the individualization of education.

The most important pedagogical problem of today is the organization of the transfer of concrete and natural sciences, in particular, physics-mathematics, physics-astronomy, physics-chemistry, chemistry-biology, physics-geography, physics-geometry, on the basis of modularized integrative programs and textbooks. In order to solve such problems, it is necessary to determine the possibility of integration of natural sciences, its rational methods (modular integration, interdisciplinary integration) and the need to use it at different levels [5].

Natural sciences should always be combined with theoretical concepts, laws and practical training.

In the course of the research, it was proved that it is necessary to acquire knowledge, training, skills and competences related to the integration of subjects in mixed educational subjects, and the methodology of creating teaching algorithms for the purpose [6].

Many years of scientific and pedagogical experience show that the use of the following methodical methods for the purpose of integrating the teaching of subjects is effective:

Curriculums for academic subjects other than field subjects,
programs, study of educational literature, with teachers of these subjects
establishing strong creative-methodical ties.

Educational materials in the nature of science integration
selection, methodical interpretation and thorough study of them in training.

In addition to the theory of personal creative ability development, it is necessary to develop a pedagogical technology to accelerate the process of educational and creative activity of students. [7].

But in order to reach the level of acceleration technology, it is necessary to reveal the dialectic of the process of acceleration, optimization and integration of educational and creative activities.

The relevance of the problem of integration of various educational and creative activities has not lost its importance even today. Didactic research in this direction was summarized by T.I. Shamova [8], who expressed the integration of education as follows:

"It can be argued that only a student who consciously uses the science of activity in education can be active, which means that he can implement it only in the conditions where he acquires certain knowledge about the science and methods of activity" [9].

From the pedagogical point of view, intensification does not exclude integration, but suggests the use of means of integration of forms and methods of teaching and upbringing.

There can be two types of connection between disciplines: ideological connection and temporal (synchronic) connection.

Conceptual connection means the study of fundamental scientific concepts, laws and theories, basic rules in science and their application in related disciplines.

Also, the implementation of interdisciplinary methodology is important. Below are some ways to make interdisciplinary connections.

1. Scientific concepts in different subjects are compatible and mutually compatible should be interpreted as completed.
2. Generalized by topics, sections and the whole course lecture is very useful.
3. Such lectures can be used to show the importance of science in connection of sciences, change of nature and development of technology.

Implementation of integration in education is important both economically, pedagogically, hygienically and physiologically, it saves the time and energy of the student, avoids excessive stress, and makes it possible to optimize the educational process.

Many years of experience, as well as the currently available theory of chemistry teaching methodology, in introducing students to the basic laws of chemistry in high school, not the personal, somewhat shallow and abstract experience of students, but the rules of modern science, which are very suitable for students' knowledge, and, first of all, the current time about the structure of substances should be based on imagination.

In this, all the basic rules of modern science are taught not dogmatically, but using facts that students can easily understand, which help to understand the essence of the studied laws.

In order to introduce the students to the basic laws of chemistry, first of all, it is necessary to adequately justify the theoretical rules and explain to the students that the laws are not imaginary things, they only reflect the phenomena that exist in nature.

Summary

Based on the study of the literature on the emergence, development and progress of teaching chemistry on the basis of integration with other subjects in foreign countries and in our country, it was found that in the process of teaching chemistry in our country, the implementation of teaching between chemical subjects with other subjects and in mutual dependence has developed rapidly.

Based on the teaching of the chemistry course and the methods used in it, the concept of valence was formed in three stages: the initial, 1970s, 1990s, and post-independence stages of the textbooks were studied and analyzed.

Based on the didactic analysis, it was found that the textbooks used before 1970s and 1990s did not contain any information about electrochemical valence.

In the chemistry manuals and textbooks created in our country during the period of independence, it was shown that the formation and development of the concept of valency was carried out on the basis of interdisciplinary integration.

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